

THE APPLICATION OF THE PRINCIPLES OF FRACTURE MECHANICS
TO A STUDY OF THE FRACTURE OF FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM

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The fracture of 6061 aluminum alloy reinforced with unidirectional boron fibers was investigated using a) the R-curve technique, b) the critical stress intensity, K_{Ic} , c) the critical J integral value, J_{Ic} .

The material examined was a diffusion bonded 6061 aluminum alloy reinforced longitudinally with 5.6×10^{-3} in. diameter boron fibers. The nominal level of reinforcement was fifty volume percent. Center notched specimens 0.1 ins. thick and one, two and four ins. wide were electric discharge machined from the original 12 x 12 in. panels. The ratio of the gauge length to specimen width was maintained constant at 3:1, and the nominal ratios of crack length to specimen width ($2a/w$) used were 0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20, 0.40, and 0.60. Primary test data consisted of load, load point displacement, crack face displacement, and transverse strain profile near the notch tip.

It was found that the net section stress at failure was considerably below that of an unnotched specimen. The net section failure stress decreased sharply in the range $0 \leq 2a/w < 0.2$. However, for $2a/w \geq 0.2$, this stress remained approximately constant for a given specimen size.

The data describing the transverse strain profile near the notch tip was analyzed to determine the order of the stress field singularity near the notch tip. The strains measured coplanar with the crack were compared to the strains implied by the following stress field equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_y &= [K_I/(2\pi r)^{1/2}][\rho/2r] + [K_I/(2\pi r)^{1/2}] \\ \sigma_x &= \{-[K_I/(2\pi r)^{1/2}][\rho/2r] + [K_I/(2r)^{1/2}]\} \{E_{xx}/E_{yy}\}^{1/2}\end{aligned}$$

These equations appeared to describe the variation of strain with distance reasonably accurately. However, the absolute values of strain predicted by these equations were considerably greater than those actually measured. It was therefore concluded that the concentration of stress resulting from the center notch was much less than that expected from a totally elastic material. The deviation between the elastic strains expected and those actually measured increased as the applied load increased indicating that appreciable plastic flow was occurring at the crack tip.

It was deduced from the crack face displacement data and computer modeling

that extensive shear yielding occurred along a line parallel to the fibers and above the notch tip. An approximate formula to predict the extent of this shear yielding as a function of applied stress was derived. Based on this approximate shear lag model, an equation predicting the crack face displacement as a function of applied stress was derived. Reasonable agreement was obtained between the predictions of this model and the experimental data.

The stress intensity factors at failure and the R-curves obtained from the material did not seem to reflect properties that were common to all the specimens. However, since the effective crack size at failure was determined by a compliance technique, it was concluded that these results may merely reflect a lack of correlation between crack size and compliance. Notwithstanding, an R-curve was assumed that was unique to each specimen group and reasonable agreement between the expected and the measured fracture strengths was obtained. The critical value of the J-integral was obtained by a) comparing the failure stresses with J integral values obtained from computer evaluation of the line integral, b) evaluating J from the load-displacement records or c) evaluation using an expression developed using the shear lag model. A critical value of the J-integral of about 600 in-lbs/in² was obtained that was independent of the method of calculation.

Finally, different failure modes were observed among the specimens tested. The fracture surface of the four inch wide specimens resembled that of a brittle material, being very even with little evidence of fiber pullout. The fracture surface of the smaller specimens, however, appeared very uneven with evidence of extensive fiber pullout. This difference in failure modes was analyzed in terms of the influence of the in plane dimensions of the specimens on the stress distribution in these samples. It was concluded that edge effects in the smaller specimens could have caused alterations in the stress field in the specimens, leading to different failure modes. However, comparative materials tests revealed significant differences in the strength of the component fibers and the degree of fiber-matrix bonding between the material contained in the four inch wide specimens and that in the smaller specimens. Thus, the type of failure observed could not be directly attributed solely to specimen size.